

Study on electronic-spectral aspects with special emphasis on symmetry change around Pr³⁺ ion in solution of organic oximes

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Abstract : The change in symmetry around (stereo-environment) the doped Pr³⁺ ion in various solutions of some organic oximes has been studied for various electronic spectral parameters. The parameters viz. Slater-Condon (F_K), Lande parameter (ζ_{sp}), intensity of hypersensitive band, bonding parameter ($b^{1/2}$), Judd-Ofelt parameter (T_λ) and Racah parameter (E^K) for Pr³⁺ doped in solution of organic oximes have been studied.

Keywords : Doped systems, stereo-environment.

Introduction

Lanthanoid materials are of interest due to their numerous applications such as scintillators, visible ultraviolet (VUV) lasers, phosphors for fluorescent lighting and plasma displays, luminescent chemosensors for medical diagnostics, shift reagents for NMR spectroscopy, as well as in various industries and biological studies¹⁻⁸. Electronic spectral studies of lanthanoid ion complexes with reference to Judd-Ofelt parameters have been found to have due significance⁹. This is because of strong validity of the theory given by Judd-Ofelt for intensity of $f \leftrightarrow f$ transitions. The various parameters given by Judd-Ofelt have been used to explain covalency and symmetry around lanthanoid ion.

In the present study six organic oximes (acetoxime, acetophenoneoxime, benzophenoneoxime, diacetylmono-oxime, cyclooctanoneoxime and camphoreoxime) have been used as ligands.

Pr³⁺ ion yields four bands¹⁰⁻¹² in the visible region corresponding to ³P₂, ³P₁, ³P₀ and ¹D₂ levels. The solution of each ligand was prepared in 50% aqueous ethanol solution (v/v) and a constant volume of PrCl₃.6H₂O salt solution (w/v) has been added to this solution and spectra is measured in 390–650 nm region.

Results and discussion

The calculation of parameters viz. Judd-Ofelt (T_λ), Slater-Condon (F_K), Lande (ζ_{sp}), Racah (E^K) have been computed by the programme developed by earlier workers¹³⁻¹⁵.

The computed values of oscillator strength, Judd-Ofelt parameter (Table 1), energies of various peak, bonding parameters (Table 2), Slater-Condon (F_K), Lande (ζ_{sp}), Racah (E^K) parameters and nephelauxetic ratio (Table 3) have been tabulated.

Spectral intensity parameters :

The oscillator strength (P_{obs}) values vary from 18.5×10^{-6} to 26.7×10^{-6} for hypersensitive transition. There is much variation in Judd-Ofelt parameter, shows that the sequence $T_2 < T_4 < T_6$ is in good agreement with lanthanide metal ion characteristics. The deep lying $4f$ sub shell experiencing intense shielding make these orbitals less available for bonding, thereby leading to lesser degree of metal-ligand interactions. The ratio T_4/T_6 indicates symmetry around the cation and varies from 0.2011–0.3617.

In the present study the doped Pr³⁺ ion systems have been classified according to their T_4/T_6 ratio value. The following inference regarding the symmetry of stereo

Table 1. Computed values of oscillator strength and Judd-Ofelt parameters

Sl. no.	Systems	M:L	Oscillator strength												T_4	T_6	T_4/T_6	σ_{rms}	K
			3P_2 band		3P_1 band		3P_0 band		1D_2 band		T_2		T_4						
			P_{obs}	P_{cal}	P_{obs}	P_{cal}	P_{obs}	P_{cal}	P_{obs}	P_{cal}	$\times 10^6$	$\times 10^6$	$\times 10^9$	$\times 10^9$					
1.	Pr ³⁺ + Acetoxime	1:2	21.007	21.007	6.475	6.144	5.735	5.989	3.737	3.737	3.737	3.737	1.6927	6.4492	0.2624	1.0346	0.1449		
2.	Pr ³⁺ + Acetoxime	1:1	20.346	20.346	6.230	6.216	6.126	6.065	3.643	3.643	3.643	3.643	1.7129	6.2278	0.2750	0.1322	0.1454		
3.	Pr ³⁺ + Acetophenoneoxime	1:2	18.572	18.572	6.446	5.543	4.581	5.405	3.622	3.622	3.622	3.622	1.5309	5.7039	0.2684	3.0522	0.1452		
4.	Pr ³⁺ + Acetophenoneoxime	1:1	18.646	18.646	6.643	5.774	4.844	5.632	3.575	3.575	3.575	3.575	1.5920	5.7042	0.2790	2.9283	0.1456		
5.	Pr ³⁺ + Benzophenoneoxime	1:2	20.846	20.846	6.386	5.628	4.805	5.486	3.998	3.998	3.998	3.998	1.5562	6.4675	0.2406	2.5437	0.1442		
6.	Pr ³⁺ + Benzophenoneoxime	1:1	21.424	21.424	5.158	4.877	4.532	4.757	3.859	3.859	3.859	3.859	1.3492	6.7087	0.2011	0.8833	0.1427		
7.	Pr ³⁺ + Diacetylmonooxime	1:2	19.716	19.716	6.605	6.471	6.260	6.315	3.891	3.891	3.891	3.891	1.7818	6.0005	0.2969	0.3357	0.1462		
8.	Pr ³⁺ + Diacetylmonooxime	1:1	21.066	21.066	7.261	7.098	6.849	6.925	4.404	4.404	4.404	4.404	1.9618	6.4219	0.3054	0.4232	0.1465		
9.	Pr ³⁺ + Cyclooctanoneoxime	1:2	25.697	25.697	10.676	10.108	9.412	9.852	6.581	6.581	6.581	6.581	2.7924	7.7182	0.3617	1.7818	0.1485		
10.	Pr ³⁺ + Cyclooctanoneoxime	1:1	26.744	26.744	9.505	8.680	7.747	8.461	6.460	6.460	6.460	6.460	2.4001	8.2030	0.2925	2.7254	0.1460		
11.	Pr ³⁺ + Camphoreoxime	1:2	21.190	21.190	6.565	6.066	5.501	5.921	4.078	4.078	4.078	4.078	1.6709	6.5111	0.2566	1.6244	0.1447		
12.	Pr ³⁺ + Camphoreoxime	1:1	18.716	18.716	6.924	6.293	5.565	6.115	3.716	3.716	3.716	3.716	1.7322	5.7203	0.3028	2.0952	0.1464		

Table 2. Computed values of energies of various peaks and bonding parameters

Sl. no.	Systems	M : L	Energy of peak (cm ⁻¹)						σ_{rms}	β	$b^{1/2}$	$\delta\%$		
			³ P ₂ band		³ P ₁ band		³ P ₀ band						³ D ₂ band	
			E _{obs}	E _{cal}	E _{obs}	E _{cal}	E _{obs}	E _{cal}	E _{obs}	E _{cal}				
1.	Pr ³⁺ + Acetoxime	1 : 2	22464.4	22329.8	21264.0	21214.9	20727.7	20767.5	16851.9	17072.5	78.5	0.967	0.128	3.41
2.	Pr ³⁺ + Acetoxime	1 : 1	22460.6	22326.2	21262.0	21217.4	20743.9	20780.7	16860.9	17075.6	76.0	0.968	0.126	3.28
3.	Pr ³⁺ + Acetophenoneoxime	1 : 2	22422.0	22298.6	21212.6	21180.9	20684.5	20729.2	16838.9	17045.5	71.4	0.965	0.132	3.62
4.	Pr ³⁺ + Acetophenoneoxime	1 : 1	22451.1	22313.8	21250.0	21203.6	20725.7	20764.6	16844.6	17064.5	78.2	0.967	0.127	3.38
5.	Pr ³⁺ + Benzophenoneoxime	1 : 2	22350.7	22259.8	21187.2	21146.1	20653.6	20702.5	16824.8	17019.1	66.3	0.964	0.134	3.73
6.	Pr ³⁺ + Benzophenoneoxime	1 : 1	22366.4	22277.8	21176.8	21150.3	20628.3	20682.0	16831.8	17019.9	63.1	0.961	0.137	3.99
7.	Pr ³⁺ + Diacetylmonooxime	1 : 2	22467.1	22351.4	21275.1	21240.6	20764.5	20799.8	16899.1	17093.3	67.1	0.968	0.124	3.20
8.	Pr ³⁺ + Diacetylmonooxime	1 : 1	22383.1	22221.7	21196.3	21127.9	20678.9	20719.6	16756.3	17008.3	92.3	0.966	0.129	3.46
9.	Pr ³⁺ + Cyclooctanoneoxime	1 : 2	22406.2	22281.9	21206.8	21165.4	20669.8	20716.1	16818.7	17033.6	75.4	0.964	0.133	3.69
10.	Pr ³⁺ + Cyclooctanoneoxime	1 : 1	22316.5	22214.7	21186.6	21115.8	20652.0	20699.1	16779.3	16998.1	77.4	0.965	0.132	3.61
11.	Pr ³⁺ + Camphoreoxime	1 : 2	22477.4	22335.4	21268.3	21228.1	20759.3	20799.7	16869.2	17084.1	76.2	0.968	0.124	3.20
12.	Pr ³⁺ + Camphoreoxime	1 : 1	22339.2	22309.6	21282.2	21189.0	20680.2	20731.9	16863.3	17051.3	64.1	0.964	0.132	3.64

Table 3. Computed values of Slater-Condon, Racah and Lande parameters

Sl. no.	Systems	M:L	F_2	F_4	F_6	$\% r F_2$	ζ_{4f}	E^1	E^2	E^3	$\% r \zeta_{4f}$
1.	Pr ³⁺ (Aqua ion)	-	322.09	44.46	4.870	-	738.00	4729.00	24.78	478.13	-
2.	Pr ³⁺ + Acetoxime	1:2	311.48	43.00	4.706	3.292	655.35	4573.18	23.92	462.37	11.558
3.	Pr ³⁺ + Acetoxime	1:1	311.85	43.05	4.712	3.177	650.26	4578.58	23.95	462.91	12.244
4.	Pr ³⁺ + Acetophenoneoxime	1:2	310.81	42.90	4.696	3.499	657.17	4563.39	23.87	461.38	11.312
5.	Pr ³⁺ + Acetophenoneoxime	1:1	311.56	43.01	4.707	3.267	651.27	4574.34	23.92	462.48	12.109
6.	Pr ³⁺ + Benzophenoneoxime	1:2	310.51	42.86	4.691	3.594	653.23	4585.87	23.84	460.92	11.844
7.	Pr ³⁺ + Benzophenoneoxime	1:1	309.82	42.77	4.681	3.806	664.92	4548.83	23.79	459.90	10.266
8.	Pr ³⁺ + Diacetylmonooxime	1:2	312.09	43.08	4.715	3.102	652.32	4582.14	23.96	463.27	11.967
9.	Pr ³⁺ + Diacetylmonooxime	1:1	311.30	42.97	4.703	3.349	636.33	4570.46	23.90	462.09	14.124
10.	Pr ³⁺ + Cyclooctanoneoxime	1:2	310.64	42.88	4.693	3.552	655.96	4560.86	23.85	461.12	11.475
11.	Pr ³⁺ + Cyclooctanoneoxime	1:1	310.85	42.91	4.696	3.489	640.32	4563.85	23.87	461.42	11.586
12.	Pr ³⁺ + Camphoreoxime	1:2	312.09	43.08	4.715	3.103	649.20	4582.10	23.96	463.27	12.388
13.	Pr ³⁺ + Camphoreoxime	1:1	310.78	42.90	4.695	3.510	659.77	4562.87	23.86	461.32	10.961

environment around the doped Pr^{3+} ion systems can be drawn.

(i) Systems having the value of T_4/T_6 ratio varying in between 0.2400 to 0.2700, classified as System-A. This includes systems having ligands like acetoxime, acetophenoneoxime, benzophenoneoxime and camphoroxime with metal (Pr^{3+}) to ligand ratio 1 : 2. These have very slight deviation from symmetry.

(ii) The systems having the value of T_4/T_6 ratio varying in between 0.2700 to 0.3100, classified as System-B. This includes all the ligands of System-A, but here these have metal to ligand ratio 1 : 1. Along with these, the ligands like diacetylmonooxime and cyclooctanoneoxime also included in the System-B, irrespective to their metal to ligand ratio.

(iii) Thus, change in the T_4/T_6 ratio value suggest the two different stereo-environment around Pr^{3+} doped system (System-A and System-B) in the present study of under taken systems.

The transition ${}^3H_4 \rightarrow {}^3P_2$ behaves as a hypersensitive transition and it follows the relation $P_{\text{obs}} \propto \bar{\nu} T_6$ in the present study.

The values of proportionality constant (k) with respect to $\bar{\nu} T_6$ have been tabulated in Table 1. It's value comes to be almost constant (0.14). This conforms the relation $P_{\text{obs}} \propto \bar{\nu} T_6$ as proposed by Peacock¹⁶.

Bonding parameters :

Taking the free ion as standard the ligand cause a slight red shift of the bands. Red shift may be conveniently used as a measure of metal-ligand covalent bonding.

The effect may be visualized to be due to an expansion of wave function which results from the interactions between the metal cation and the bonding anion. The value of nephelauxetic ratio (β) has been found to be less than one in all the systems irrespective to their metal-ligand ratio. Positive value of $b^{1/2}$ indicates some covalent character in the metal-ligand bond.

Slater-Condon, Racah and Lande parameters :

The parametric values reveal a remarkable variation in spin orbit interaction parameters. Its value ranges from 636.33 to 664.92. The percentage reduction ($\% r \zeta_{4f}$) value comes to be from 10.26 to 14.12.

The decrease in values of Slater-Condon, Lande and Racah parameters of the doped systems as compared to those of free metal ion may be attributed to chelation of Pr^{3+} ion with the ligand present in the surrounding environment, and thus indicates the expansion of metal orbital which is in accordance with the theory of origin of intensity of intra- $f \leftrightarrow f$ transitions. This has also been observed that when the M : L is 1 : 2 for Pr^{3+} /acetoxime, Pr^{3+} /acetophenoneoxime and Pr^{3+} /cyclooctanoneoxime the decrease in F_2 value is more in comparison to M : L is 1 : 1 for the same ligand.

This may also support the stereo-environment classification (System-A and System-B) as revealed under spectral intensity parameter.

Materials and method :

All the chemicals and the solvent used were of analytical grade. Chloride of praseodymium having 99.99% purity was supplied by Indian Rare Earths Ltd. The ligands were dissolved to prepare 0.32 M and 0.16 M solutions in 50% aqueous ethanol (v/v) at room temperature (32 °C). Equal volume (10 ml) of each of these 0.32 M and 0.16 M ligand solution was added in 10 ml solution of 0.16 M $\text{PrCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ to get six systems each of having metal to ligand ratio 1 : 2 and 1 : 1 respectively. Solution spectra of these twelve systems were recorded by using standard spectrophotometer (Biomate UV-Visible spectro-photometer v7.07) in the range of 390 to 650 nm. Four peaks corresponding to ${}^3H_4 \rightarrow {}^3P_2$, ${}^3H_4 \rightarrow {}^3P_1$, ${}^3H_4 \rightarrow {}^3P_0$ and ${}^3H_4 \rightarrow {}^1D_2$ transitions were observed.

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